

Newsletter, Issue 3

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RI-PATHS State of Play

The RI-PATHS team has concluded a highly interactive and participatory phase of the project which was dedicated to sourcing input from the Research Infrastructure (RI) community on key building blocks for developing a comprehensive framework on socio-economic impact. In total, nine participatory workshops have been convened helping the RI-PATHS team to identify the key areas for impact measurement, to disentangle main impact pathways for various types of RIs, to structure draft lists of suitable indicators and to assess the applicability of a range of measurement methods. The results of these interactive events are summarised in two reports: [D4.1 Concept note on modular impact assessment framework](#) and D4.2 Results of the participatory workshops (available end July 2019).

As the next step, the RI-PATHS team will refine the conceptual framework and discuss it with the project Advisory Board in September 2019. The RI community, policy makers and other interested stakeholders are warmly invited to a [validation workshop of the RI-PATHS impact assessment framework on 22 October 2019 in Brussels](#) (Fraunhofer EU Office, Rue Royale 94).

High-level Expert Groups on Research Infrastructures

The RI-PATHS coordinator EFIS Centre is engaged in two High-Level Expert Groups on Research Infrastructures that are relevant to the area of impact assessment.

1. ESFRI AD-HOC WORKING GROUP

In May 2018, the Competitiveness Council adopted conclusions on Accelerating knowledge circulation in the EU which invites Member States and the Commission within the framework of ESFRI "to develop a common approach for monitoring of their Research Infrastructures (RIs) performance and invited the Pan-European RIs, on a voluntary basis, to include it in their governance and explore options to support this through the use of Key Performance Indicators".

ESFRI was asked to implement this mandate and set up an ad hoc working group (WG) whose Terms of Reference (ToRs) define its objective as follows:

"...to consolidate the existing knowledge on monitoring of RI performance, propose a common approach at European level and explore options to support this through the use of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Such KPIs must be easy to use, shall be adjustable to different systems and types of RIs (new as well as existing) and yet robust to ensure high a level of confidence. They could serve as one element of the monitoring carried out by RIs and their governance bodies to monitor their performance."

Alasdair Reid, Policy Director of EFIS Centre and coordinator of RI-PATHS, was invited to join an [ad-hoc working group on monitoring and KPIs](#) to develop a suitable framework that could be applied to the ESFRI Landmarks. The working group met several time in the first semester of 2019 and developed a proposal (including detailed summary sheets for a proposed set of 20 KPIs) that will be presented at an ESFRI Validation Workshop on "[Monitoring of Research Infrastructures Methodology and Key Performance Indicators](#)" in Brussels on 3 July 2019. The work of RI-PATHS on indicators for socio-economic impact assessment (IA) was taken into account by the ad hoc working group and the need for RIs to monitor a core set of KPIs over time that allows the development of an evidence base for subsequent IAs was underlined.

2. EUROPEAN COMMISSION HIGH-LEVEL EXPERT GROUP

In January 2019, the European Commission DG Research and Innovation (DG RTD) set up a High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) to assess the progress of ESFRI and Other World Class Research Infrastructures towards implementation and long-term sustainability. Jelena Angelis, Research Director of EFIS Centre, was invited to join the HLEG together with another four independent experts from France, Italy, Portugal and the United Kingdom.

The HLEG focuses on two complementary objectives:

- Assessment of the effectiveness of the RI funding instruments under the Union Framework Programme, in particular the preparatory phase funding for RIs in early phases of their lifecycle, the individual support for fostering their implementation and enhancing their sustainability and to provide recommendations, where appropriate for improvements.
- Assessment sustainability of the RI progress towards implementation and long-term, i.e.:
- Evaluate the future outlook of the pan-European (or global) relevance RIs in relation to their scientific goals and the evolution in their lifecycle;
- Identify major bottlenecks and possible measures which might impact their further development;
- Provide recommendations on the basis of the assessment and evaluation in line with the Long-term sustainability pre-conditions, namely critical mass and added value of the RI (in comparison with a network) and prospection of new members;
- Key Performance Indicators and Socio-Economic Impact;
- Catalogue of services and service-driven approach;
- User communities and outputs also in terms of innovation and TRLs;
- Capacity to maintain leadership and excellence in terms of instrumentation and services in relation to scientific and technical developments;
- Complementarity of the activities of the RIs and possibilities for consolidation with overlapping/related RIs;
- Effectiveness of embedding international partners in the RI and of the cooperation with relevant international partners.

First results of the work will be ready in July 2019 but the whole work will be concluded in December 2019.

Second round of participatory workshops

Between 8th and 10th May 2019, the second round of RI-PATHS workshops took place at the premises of DESY and ALBA as well as close to the ELIXIR campus in Whittlesford. The main aim of this second round was to engage the RI community more in-depth in the identification of suitable indicators and metrics that can in practice serve to measure the main aspects and impact pathways that were identified as relevant and feasible in the first round of workshops. Hence, the workshops focused on sourcing consensus on the selection of relevant indicators and discussions on data gathering routines that could be deployed in future IA exercises. The workshops were structured keeping in mind the objective of exploring more in-depth each of the three main domains of impact assessment identified

- Straightforward impacts to be robustly captured in economic analysis,
- Non-quantifiable impacts captured by actor-based analysis,
- Complex network effects captured through exploratory approaches.

Each workshop started with a short presentation of the project and its key milestones, before the consortium team proposed a structure of pathways and a potential core indicator system based on outcomes from T2.4. Subsequently, the workshop participants were asked to scrutinise and develop further the proposed framework with a view to both relevance and feasibility. As a follow up, a survey was sent to all participants (as well as the broader RI-PATHS community) who were asked to review and comment on long-lists of pathways and indicators. Based on this detailed engagement, the workshops resulted in a corroboration (and in part readjustment) of assumptions that will shape both the project's guiding model and the more detailed indicator system to be attached to it.

The first workshop at **DESY** (Hamburg) focused on methodologies to measure **quantifiable economic impacts of research infrastructures**, drawing and elaborating on the CBA methodology developed by CSIL. Concrete experiences with economic impact assessments were presented by the host (DESY, DORIS study) and by CERN. Subsequently, participants were invited to comment on and rank indicators used in this methodology by importance and add those that they found missing.

The second workshop at **ELIXIR** (Whittlesford Parkway) focused on possible **new ways of documenting network effects in research, innovation and training**, building on introductory presentation from the EFIS Centre team. Concrete experiences were shared by the host (ELIXIR) as well as by CERIC-ERIC. Subsequently, participants were invited to comment on ways to assess and evaluate impact along those impact pathways that cannot be captured easily in economic terms.

Despite interference by an air traffic control strike, the third workshop at **ALBA** (Cerdanyola del Vallès) explored **impact-relevant interactions between RIs and users** - focusing less on the estimate extent of impact itself, but more on ways to establish the extent of relevant interactions with users. These

provide valuable information in themselves and, in addition, allow us to take suitable assumptions in later estimations. Concrete experiences were shared by the host (ALBA) and ELI. Subsequently, the RI-PATHS team intended to engage the participants in in-depth discussions on existing long lists of suitable indicators for selected pathways.

An additional participatory workshop was held in conjunction with the final event of the MERIL-2 project on 24th June in Lisbon. The discussions focused on topics regarding: 1) **commonalities and differences in IA needs** between different types and domains of RIs, in particular distinctions between natural science RIs and RIs serving social sciences and humanities; 2) **resource needs to carry out IA activities**; as well as 3) **usage and openness of impact related data**.

In summary, the workshops resulted in several central findings:

First, a majority of research infrastructures agree that societal and human capital impact can be as important as economic - and in part even scientific - impact. In particular, distributed research infrastructures see societal impact on equal terms with their impact in the pure scientific domain. At least within the RI community built around RI-PATHS project it is undeniably confirmed that an exclusively scientific orientations constitute the exception rather than the rule, even among single site, hard science infrastructures.

Figure 1: Assessment of Relevance of different impact categories (mostly single-sited, "hard science" infrastructures)

Source: own kahoot! on-site survey, 08/05/2019

Figure 2: Assessment of Relevance of different impact categories (mostly distributed, partially "soft science" infrastructures)

Source: own kahoot! on-site survey, 09/05/2019, N=21-24

Second, however, the majority of research infrastructure managers are rather pessimistic about the means available. Many are aware of the opportunities that bibliometrics and cost-benefit analysis provide, but even within those domains many technical problems remain. With a view to societal impact, many RI managers lack a clear concept or a mission that is sufficiently articulated to attach valid measurements or indicators. Accordingly, most of them remain unaware and do not consciously collect information on the different types of exchanges by means of which their research infrastructure interacts to society.

Third, there is surprising agreement on at least some fundamental indicators that many RI managers would like to see collected. At the same time, their motivation for this is split between information that they would like to see collected with a view to their mission and such that they agree needs to be collected for policy makers - without necessarily making sense in substance. Overall, there is a remaining wariness to define too many indicators that are essentially "off mission" - in particular in a situation where broad missions allow many indicators that satisfy both policy and management needs (see above).

Fourth, it becomes increasingly clear that the logics of impact creation and causation are fundamentally different between single-site and distributed virtual infrastructures. While they still have to contribute to the same overarching societal targets and hence

impact domains, they do so through notably different impact pathways. Overall, their function as game-changers not only within the domain of research infrastructures but for research at large remains substantially underacknowledged. Currently, we have very limited means to document the new avenues of co-creation that they enable.

Fifth, there is a notable tension between (strict) principles of open access and the abovementioned need to document complex network effects. Even if legally barred from IP-tracing users, distributed and virtual RIs, have a broad array of IT-based means available to understand - or at least document - the networks that they are creating - which in turn would allow assumptions on pathways and impact created. In practice, however, they tend to forego most this great potential by deciding against any process of registering users for reasons based on (strict) open access credentials.

Finally, the workshops provided general confirmation on the array of impact pathways as well as many of the indicators that this project has so far put forward - including important elements of semantic fine-tuning in both areas. Taking into account the needed differentiations between single-sited and distributed infrastructures and certain differences between RIs in "hard" vs. "soft" science, the RI-PATHS project's conceptual model has now arrived at a degree of maturity that allows to initiate concrete piloting efforts in collaboration with RI partners.

Publications

Research infrastructures boost to industry and economy. In a paper on L'industria, RI-PATHS' staff Silvia Vignetti and Francesco Giffoni discuss how to estimate the socioeconomic impact of Research Infrastructures and investments in science. They argue that evaluation is essential to justify publicly-funded and costly investments yet challenging. Their critical review of

existing methodologies to assess the impact of RIs focuses on the Cost-benefit Analysis (CBA) as one of the analytical frameworks for evaluating welfare changes attributable to RIs. Indeed, the use of shadow prices, along with other techniques

l'industria

(e.g. willingness-to-pay and avoided costs), captures the social opportunity costs of goods and services and allows the evaluation of non-market impacts.

CSIL's Massimo Florio, Francesco Giffoni, Anna Giunta and Emanuela Sirtori have recently published a [study on how public procurement by big research infrastructures enhances suppliers' performance on Industrial and Corporate Change](#). Using survey data on 669 CERN's suppliers, they built a unique data set to analyse the determinants of suppliers' sales, profits, and development activities. They found out that collaborative relations between CERN and its suppliers improved suppliers' performance and increased positive spill-overs along the supply chain. This insight suggested that public procurement, as mission-oriented innovation policy, should promote cooperative relations and not only market mechanisms.

Industrial and
Corporate Change

Journal of Economic
Policy Reform

For another research, Massimo Florio, Francesco Giffoni and Jessica Catalano interviewed 1,022 undergraduates to study the drivers of preferences for paying for basic research, which are still little known. Moreover, taxpayers are usually the ultimate funders of large-scale research infrastructures, but the expected discoveries of such projects often do not have any known use-value. CSIL's researchers focused on the LHC at CERN, where the Higgs boson was discovered and found out that income, awareness, and positive attitudes towards science drive a positive willingness-to-pay for science. Social sciences and the humanities' students resulted willing to contribute to fundamental research at least as much as their peers in science curricula. Findings suggest support to government funding of basic research as a public good. Their article "[Should governments fund basic science? Evidence from a willingness-to-pay experiment in five universities](#)" was published by Taylor & Francis Group's Journal of Economic Policy Reform.

RI-PATHS at the AESIS Impact of Science Conference

On 6th June 2019, Henning Kroll participated in the AESIS Conference in Berlin as an invited speaker, presenting findings from the RI-PATHS projects in a session on co-creation. In his presentation, he emphasised various forms of underacknowledged interactions along impact pathways. The subsequent discussion reaffirmed earlier findings in the project such as the transformative nature of distributed infrastructures and

the potential tension between open access and impact documentation. In the larger debate on the conference, the RI-PATHS contributions positioned itself clearly in favour of studying pathways and understanding logics - against big data inspired proposition that understanding the concrete mechanisms of causation may in fact no longer be necessary as long as outcomes can be predicted. Nonetheless, the conference demonstrated that big data approaches may provide relevant inspiration for subsequent project work with a view to tracing impact and impact pathways in area previously inaccessible.

The Network for Advancing and Evaluating the Societal Impact of Science (AESIS) is an international, open community for various types of professionals working on stimulating and demonstrating the impact of science on economy, culture and well-being. It seeks to contribute towards an increased sharing of best practices to develop effective instruments for evaluating and advancing the societal impact of science. The Impact of Science conference 2019 took place from 5th to 7th June in Berlin, Germany, involving high-level participation from the German Chancellery, the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research, several Research Councils, leading Research Organisations and diverse private sector analysts (<http://aesisnet.com/event/ios19/>).

Engagement with other related projects

In the course of the project, members of the RI-PATHS team have engaged with similar EU-funded projects to source further inspiration on the concept and methodologies for impact assessment. In particular, there were exchanges with the projects **ACCELERATE** (www.accelerate2020.eu, led by CERIC-ERIC), **ResInfra** (<http://www.interreg-danube.eu/approved-projects/resinfra-dr>, led by Centre for Social Innovation) and **Data4Impact** (www.data4impact.eu, led by PPMI) at both working and strategic levels.

The **ACCELERATE project** is supporting the long-term sustainability of large scale research infrastructures (RIs) through the development of policies and legal and administrative tools for a more effective management and operation of RIs, with a special focus on ERICs and CERIC in particular. Discussions were held with senior staff and

researchers at the Rathenau Instituut, a main supporting research partner that, in the ACCELERATE project assumes part of the role of the core partners within RI-PATHS. Since the findings and approach of the two projects speak to each other rather directly RI-PATHS has included some insights from ACCELERATE e.g. in establishing its indicator long-list.

The **ResInfra project** aims to improve framework conditions for research infrastructure and innovation in the Danube region.

This project facilitates enhanced transnational cooperation and a macro-regional scope of the sustainable development of research infrastructures.

During the project, the ResInfra team

has developed guidelines for RIs on ex-ante evaluation, as well as collected a dataset of competent and qualified reviewers for RI assessments. RI-PATHS team has contributed with a presentation delivered at ResInfra event. Also, the RI-PATHS literature review has been consulted and references by ResInfra team in the preparation of the evaluation guide to RIs.

The **Data4Impact project** develops Big Data approaches for improved assessment of the societal impact in the Health, Demographic Change and Wellbeing Societal Challenge. Coordinated by PPMI, RI-PATHS core partner Fraunhofer ISI also takes a relevant role in this project. Although it is less directly related in terms of overall ambition and substance, it provides interesting perspectives on emerging options and remaining limitations in the field of novel methodologies, so that an exchange has proven fruitful on different levels. More specifically, a researcher engaged in Data4Impact has taken part in a 2nd round RI-PATHS workshop to contribute his perspectives and, in turn, learn more about the RI-PATHS effort.

Calendar of events

Past events where RI-PATHS project was presented

- **ESFRI RIs-EOSC Liaison Workshop** (30 January 2019, London, UK)
[Learn more](#)
- **ESFRI as the Strategic Forum to Develop a Common Methodology for Monitoring Research Infrastructures** (31 January 2019, London, UK) [Learn more](#)
- **RI-PATHS Participatory Workshop at DESY** (8 May 2019, Hamburg, Germany)
[Learn more](#)
- **RI-PATHS Participatory Workshop at ELIXIR** (9 May 2019, Cambridge, UK)
[Learn more](#)

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 RI-PATHS Participatory Workshop at ALBA (10 May 2019, Barcelona, Spain) [Learn more](#)
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Impact of Science 2019: Understanding causalities, correlations and pre-conditions for the different dimensions of societal impact of science (5-7 June 2019, Berlin, Germany) [Learn more](#)
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 RI-PATHS Participatory Workshop at MERIL-2 Conference (25 June 2019, Lisbon, Portugal) [Learn more](#)
-
International Future Circular Collider (FCC) Conference (24-28 June 2019, Brussels, Belgium) [Learn more](#)

Upcoming events with RI-PATHS participation

ESFRI VALIDATION WORKSHOP ON "MONITORING OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES METHODOLOGY AND KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS"

Brussels, Belgium

[Learn more](#)

RI-PATHS VALIDATION WORKSHOP

Brussels, Belgium

More information on RI-PATHS projects and events on our website www.ri-paths.eu

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